

Organizational Culture and Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers

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Abstract:

Studying organizational culture and job satisfaction among teachers is essential for creating a supportive work environment that promotes teacher well-being, enhances performance, and ultimately improves student outcomes. In this premise, this study aimed to determine the level of organizational culture and job satisfaction of private teachers in a highly urbanized city in Central Negros during the School Year 2023-2024. Data needed for this descriptive study was collected from 186 private school teachers using a self-made data-gathering instrument that has hurdled the stringent tests of validity and reliability. Teachers got high levels of organizational culture and job satisfaction; most teachers surveyed were found to be single with shorter lengths of service, encompassing a broad range of ages and average monthly income. The findings of the organizational culture within these private schools revealed a high level, especially in terms of shared goals and effective communication, while noting a deficiency in rewards and recognition. Job satisfaction was generally high among respondents, with contentment evident in fringe benefits, workplace environment, and organizational policies, although demographic differences led to varying satisfaction levels. The research established a significant relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction, highlighting the important role that institutional culture plays in shaping the educational work environment. The findings suggest that enhancing certain aspects of organizational culture may positively impact the overall sense of commitment and satisfaction among private school teachers.

Keywords: Education, organizational culture, job satisfaction, private school teachers, Negros Occidental, Philippines

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

In private schools, the organizational culture has emerged as a critical problem influencing teacher job satisfaction and commitment. Multiple factors within the school's cultural framework, such as its mission, leadership styles, policies, and available support, play a significant role in shaping a teacher's workplace experience and overall contentment with their role. Research by Murtedjo and Suharningsih (2016) suggests that while a supportive and positive organizational culture can bolster job satisfaction, enhance commitment, and improve performance, a negative or high-stress culture can lead to dissatisfaction and decreased performance.

The issue is further complicated by the leadership styles employed within the organization. Transformational leadership has been linked to positive outcomes regarding job satisfaction and organizational commitment and, in turn, to improved teacher performance (MacNeil et al., 2009). However, despite these insights, many private schools experience substantial turnover, with a notable number of teachers, sometimes as high as 5 to 10 yearly, resigning from their positions. This frequent turnover necessitates a continuous cycle of recruiting and training new staff, often fresh graduates who may require significant time to reach full proficiency.

This turnover points to a deeper issue within the organizational culture and commitment levels in private schools, leading to a recurring pattern where teachers leave the private sector for opportunities in public education. The consistent departure of teachers places a strain on private school resources. It disrupts educational continuity, indicating a crucial problem requiring attention to retain skilled educators and maintain a stable teaching workforce.

Current State of Knowledge

Job satisfaction among teachers is multifaceted and influenced by various organizational factors. Leadership style serves as a crucial element in this matrix; democratic leadership, which involves teachers in decision-making and values their input, is associated with higher job satisfaction compared to autocratic styles. This participatory approach to leadership can enhance teachers' sense of job fulfillment (Bhatti et al., 2021).

Another significant aspect is the organizational culture's impact on job stress and work-life balance. A strong correlation exists between these factors and a teacher's career satisfaction. Excessive job stress can disrupt work-life balance, leading to reduced job and career satisfaction (Çobanoğlu et al., 2023). A supportive organizational culture that mitigates stressors and promotes work-life harmony is thus essential.

Furthermore, according to Ak (2018), fair treatment and opportunities for advancement within an organization also contribute to job satisfaction. Transparent and equitable policies for recognition and promotion within schools are crucial because they directly influence employee satisfaction and morale.

In addition, the link between job satisfaction and teacher performance must be noticed. A substantial volume of research indicates that job satisfaction directly and significantly affects teacher performance. Schools are encouraged to closely monitor and enhance satisfaction levels to improve educational outcomes (Murtedjo & Suharningsih, 2016). By integrating democratic leadership, fair treatment, a supportive organizational culture, and mechanisms that promote work-life balance, educational institutions can foster a thriving environment that enhances job satisfaction and teacher performance.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Schein's Organizational Culture Theory (1980) posits that organizational culture comprises a set of shared beliefs, values, norms, and practices that govern how individuals within an organization interact and work together. The school's culture would significantly influence private school teachers' job satisfaction. Understanding the culture is critical for leaders who aim to implement change or improve the work environment. Schein's model suggests that any attempt to enhance job satisfaction must begin with a deep understanding of the underlying cultural artifacts, espoused beliefs, and core values.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory: Maslow's theory proposes that individuals are motivated by a hierarchy of needs, starting with basic physiological needs and ending with self-actualization. In the context of job satisfaction, teachers' needs could range from salary and job security (physiological and safety needs) to a sense of belonging and esteem (social and ego-status needs) and, finally, to professional growth and fulfillment (self-actualization). When these needs are met, job satisfaction is likely to be enhanced. Since organizational culture affects fulfilling these needs, understanding this connection is important for the research.

By integrating these theories, the research explored how the organizational culture in private schools meets or fails to meet the various levels of needs according to Maslow's hierarchy, thus influencing job satisfaction. Commitment levels among teachers could be indicative of where they currently find themselves within this hierarchy. A culture that supports growth, learning, and acknowledgment of achievements could foster higher satisfaction and commitment.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of organizational culture and job satisfaction of private teachers in a highly urbanized city in Central Negros during the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, this aimed to determine: 1) the level of organizational culture of private school teachers in shared goals and vision, effective communication, and rewards and recognition; 2) level of job satisfaction of private school teachers in fringe benefits, working environment and policies and guidelines; 3) significant difference in the level of organizational culture of private school teachers when grouped according to the same variables; 4) significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers when grouped according to the same variables; and 5) significant relationship between the level of organizational culture and the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers.

Research Methodology:

This section presents the methodology of the study. It discusses the research design, the study's locale, respondents, and the data-gathering procedure, including the research instrument, the test of its validity and reliability, the analytical schemes, and the statistical tools.

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive research design to determine the level of organizational culture. This design is a scientific method that involves observing and describing the behavior of a subject without influencing it in any way (Raj et al., 2024). It is often used as a precursor to quantitative research designs, with the general overview giving some valuable pointers as to what variables are worth quantitative testing (Shuttleworth, 2021). This design aims to describe a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically. It is an appropriate choice when the research aims to identify characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories (Uwase, 2020).

Respondents

The study's respondents were 186 private school teachers from a total population of 359 in three private schools in Central Negros, chosen via stratified sampling using the Cochran formula. The researcher randomly selected the respondents from each school using the lottery technique.

Instrument

This study used a self-made questionnaire to gather all the data, mainly from teacher respondents. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: Part 1 contains queries on respondents' profiles such as age, civil status, length of service, and Family Income, while Part 2A contains the questionnaire proper on the level of organizational culture with five line items each for shared goals and vision, effective communication, and rewards and recognition, while 2B for the level of job satisfaction with five line items for fringe benefits, working environment, and policies and guidelines. Each item was rated on a scale of 1 to 5, where 5 was interpreted as always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 as rarely, and 1 as almost never.

Data Collection

For the smoother conduct of the study, the researcher sought permission from the School Principals to undertake the study. Accordingly, a letter request was sent to the school principal, and upon approval, the researcher scheduled the questionnaire's administration for the respondents and the researcher in a mutually convenient manner. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the target respondents. A brief orientation was given to present the study's objectives and explain how to answer the survey questionnaire. The researcher assured the respondents that all data gathered in this study was treated with the utmost confidentiality.

Objectives

Objectives 1-2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as statistical tools to determine the level of organizational culture and job satisfaction of private school teachers when grouped according to variables. Objectives 3-4 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U-Test to determine whether a significant difference exists in the level of organizational culture and job satisfaction of private school teachers when grouped according to selected variables. Finally, objective 5 utilized a relational analytical scheme and Spearman Rho to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the organizational culture level and private school teachers' job satisfaction.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that no personal data compromising the respondents' identity was collected in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, specifically on accessing the data both by the researcher and the analyst. The researcher was the only person with access to all data gathered. The respondents assured that no information that disclosed their identity was released or published without their consent to the disclosure, except when necessary to protect their rights and welfare. Likewise, all collected materials will be appropriately disposed of by machine shredding or dissolved in water after the study's publication. Furthermore, soft copies of the data will be deleted with no chance of future retrieval.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results pertaining to the objectives of this study.

Level of Organizational Culture of Private School Teachers in Shared Goals and Vision, Effective Communication, and Rewards and Recognition

Table 1
Level of Organizational Culture of Private School Teachers in Shared Goals and Vision

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Shared Goals and Mission		
<i>Our organization.....</i>		
1. effectively communicates shared goals and vision to all staff members.	4.24	High Level
2. is aligns activities/plans to the overall vision and mission of the institution.	4.32	High Level
3. Collaborate with teachers and encourage them to achieve common objectives and vision.	4.31	High Level
4. Integrate the goals and visions into their daily teaching practices and decision-making processes.	4.29	High Level
5. motivates and inspires teachers with the shared goals and vision of the school.	4.15	High Level
Overall Mean	4.26	High Level

Table 1 shows the level of organizational culture of the private school teachers in the area of shared goals and mission. The overall mean score is 4.26, interpreted as "high level."

Item No. 2 obtained the highest mean score of 4.32, which states "it aligns activities/plans to the overall vision and mission of the institution," interpreted as "high level." At the same time, Item No. 5 got the lowest mean score of 4.15, which states "motivates and inspires teachers by the shared goals and vision of the school," interpreted as "high level."

These findings indicate potential areas for improvement in how organizational culture motivates and aligns with teachers. A potential cause for concern is that teachers might feel disconnected from the school's goals, leading to reduced motivation and investment in the school's mission, adversely affecting morale and teamwork.

This is supported by Briška & Siliņa-Jasjukeviča (2020), who suggested that a lack of teacher involvement in goal setting and vision development might contribute to this disconnect.

Table 2
Level of Organizational Culture of Private School Teachers in Effective Communication

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Effective Communication		
<i>Our organization.....</i>		
1. facilitates effective information dissemination through appropriate communication channels.	4.03	High Level
2. encourages teachers to express their opinions and ideas openly during discussions and meetings.	4.01	High Level
3. utilized communication through effective feedback mechanisms, such as teacher evaluations and surveys.	4.02	High Level
4. engage administrators and staff in regular communication to address academic concerns.	4.22	High Level
5. promptly address and resolve communication barriers, such as unclear directives or insufficient information sharing.	3.96	High Level
Overall Mean	4.05	High Level

Table 2 shows the level of organizational culture of the private school teachers in effective communication. The overall mean score is 4.05, interpreted as "high level."

Item No. 4 registered the highest mean score of 4.22, which states, "4. engage administrators and staff in regular communication to address academic concerns" interpreted as "high level," while Item No. 5 obtained the lowest mean score of 3.96 which states "promptly address and resolves communication barriers, such as unclear directives or insufficient information sharing" interpreted as "high level."

Clear instructions or a lack of proper information sharing among teachers can avoid confusion and lead to misunderstandings about expectations, processes, or roles, which might result in mistakes or reduced efficiency. Teachers typically have substantial workloads encompassing a range of responsibilities that can interfere with their ability to quickly resolve communication problems.

Meister & Melnick (2023) corroborate this in their work "National New Teacher Study: Beginning Teachers' Concerns," which underscores that new teachers often struggle with classroom and time management, as well as communication with parents, partly due to the burden of a heavy workload that impedes timely communication.

Table 3
Level of Organizational Culture of Private School Teachers in Rewards and Recognition

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Rewards and Recognition		
<i>Our organization.....</i>		
1. recognizes teachers' achievements and contributions to the school community.	4.05	High Level
2. provides clear and transparent criteria for rewards and recognition within the school.	3.74	High Level
3. acknowledges and celebrates the accomplishments of teachers in various forums or events.	3.73	High Level
4. values and appreciates teachers' efforts in promoting student success and school improvement.	3.84	High Level
5. provides opportunities for professional growth and development linked to recognition and rewards for teachers.	3.74	High Level
Overall Mean	3.82	High Level

Table 3 reveals the level of organizational culture of the private school teachers in terms of rewards and recognition. The overall mean score is 3.82, interpreted as "high level."

Item No. 1 showed the highest mean score of 4.05, which states "recognizes teachers' achievements and contributions to the school community," interpreted as "high level." At the same time, Item No. 3 got the lowest mean score of 3.73, which states "acknowledges and celebrates the accomplishments of teachers in various forums or events," interpreted as "high level."

The situation indicates an absence of formal mechanisms or programs for recognizing teachers' achievements, with staff needing more time to organize or participate in appreciation events. Budget constraints further limit the capacity for events that celebrate teacher success. Consequently, teacher recognition is not emphasized within the institution's organizational culture.

Green's (2021) study "Developing leadership: A paradox in academe" supports this view, suggesting that how educational institutions acknowledge and groom their leaders—and, by extension, recognize staff accomplishments—mirror academic values but do not always meet practical necessities, leading to a disconnect in recognition practices.

Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers in Fringe Benefits, Working Environment, and Policies and Guidelines

Table 4
Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers in Fringe Benefits

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Fringe Benefits		
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with the following:</i>		
1. 13th month pay.	4.26	High Level
2. medical allowance.	3.59	High Level
3. loyalty pays.	3.13	Moderate Level
4. financial assistance during training.	3.24	Moderate Level
5. leave benefits.	3.28	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.50	High Level

Table 4 presents the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers in the area of fringe benefits. The overall mean score is 3.50, interpreted as "high level."

Item No. 1 got the highest mean score of 4.26 which states "13th-month pay," interpreted as "high level," while Item No. 3 obtained the lowest mean score of 3.13, which states "loyalty pays," interpreted as "moderate level."

The findings indicate that teachers are dissatisfied with how their loyalty is financially compensated. They perceive their fringe benefits as uncompetitive compared to those offered in other private schools or public sector positions. The lack of a systematic approach to enhancing benefits with tenure has led teachers to feel that their loyalty is not adequately rewarded.

Further corroborating this sentiment, the study "An Inquiry into Job Satisfaction Habits among Private Secondary School Teachers in Kenya" by Immaculate & Grace discusses similar job satisfaction issues. It suggests that inadequate compensation and benefits contribute to teachers' dissatisfaction, affecting how they perceive the relationship between their loyalty to the institution and the rewards they receive in return within the private schooling sector.

Table 5
Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers in Working Environment

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Working Environment		
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with the following:</i>		
1. my number of hours teaching loads.	3.94	High Level
2. the subjects that I am handling.	4.29	High Level
3. the support of my school heads and peers.	4.18	High Level
4. the physical environment of the school.	4.08	High Level
5. the other instructional needs provided.	4.02	High Level
Overall Mean	4.10	High Level

Table 5 shows the level of job satisfaction of the Private School Teachers in the working environment. The overall mean score is 4.10, interpreted as "high level."

Item No. 2 obtained the highest mean score of 4.29, which states "the subjects that I am handling" interpreted as "high level," while Item No. 1 got the lowest mean score of 3.94, which states "my number of hours teaching loads," interpreted as "high level."

This result indicates that some teachers with a high number of teaching hours can infringe on personal time, leading to an imbalance between work and life, which can decrease satisfaction with the job. A heavier teaching load can result in increased stress levels, which can hurt job satisfaction and overall well-being.

This was agreed upon by Skaalvik & Skaalvik (2019), who found that the concept of work overload among teachers, a higher number of work assignments, and increased time pressure are positively correlated with teacher burnout and negatively correlated with job satisfaction. The research indicates that as the workload and teaching hours increase, teachers have less time for rest and recovery, which can exacerbate stress levels and reduce overall job satisfaction. This evidence highlights the challenges associated with heavy teaching loads and the importance of finding a balance to ensure the well-being and job satisfaction of teachers.

Table 6
Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers in Policies and Guidelines

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Policies and Guidelines		
<i>As a teacher, I am satisfied with the following:</i>		
1. hiring/selection.	4.12	High Level
2. promotion/transfer.	3.85	High Level
3. implementation of various programs.	3.87	High Level
4. administrative matters.	3.78	High Level
5. training/workshops.	3.44	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.81	High Level

Table 6 presents the level of job satisfaction of the public elementary school teachers in the area policies and guidelines. The overall mean score is 3.81, interpreted as "high level."

Item No. 1 registered the highest mean score of 4.12, which states "hiring/selection," interpreted as "high level." At the same time, Item No. 5 obtained the lowest mean score of 3.44, which states "training/workshops," interpreted as "moderate level."

This implies that some teachers find that if the training content is not directly applicable to their daily teaching practice or does not address their specific needs, teachers may find it unhelpful. Some training sessions may be isolated events without a clear connection to a broader professional development plan. As noted in some reports, workshops can be fragmented, leading to a lack of continuity in professional development efforts.

Studies such as "Reflective Teaching Perceived and Practiced by EFL Teachers - A Case in the South of Vietnam" highlight that workshops can sometimes be perceived as not conducive to a continuous professional development process and not relevant to teachers' actual needs, leading to dissatisfaction with training sessions (Hung & Thuy, 2021). Additionally, feedback from workshop participants suggests a need for more pedagogical training opportunities designed according to effective adult learning principles (Rauschert et al., 2018).

Level of Organizational Culture of Private School Teachers in Shared Goals and Vision, Effective Communication, and Rewards and Recognition when grouped according to Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Family Income

Table 7
Difference in the Level of Organizational Culture of Private School Teachers in Shared Goals and Vision when grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	99	95.67	4092.000	0.552	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	87	91.03				
Civil Status	Single	101	100.18	3617.500	0.061		Not Significant
	Married	85	85.56				

Length of Service	Shorter	99	93.31	4287.500	0.958	Not Significant
	Longer	87	93.72			
Family Income	Lower	91	92.63	4243.000	0.826	Not Significant
	Higher	95	94.34			

Table 7 indicates the difference in the level of organizational culture of private school teachers in shared goals and vision.

When respondents were grouped according to age, civil status, length of service, and Family Income, the computed Mann-Whitney U test were 4092.00, 3617.500, 4287.500, and 4243.000 with *p*-values of 0.552, 0.061, 0.958, and 0.826, all variables are higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Hence, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of organizational culture of private school teachers in shared goals and vision implementation when grouped according to age, civil status, length of service, and Family Income was therefore "accepted."

This suggests that age, civil status, length of service, and Family Income do not significantly impact the teachers' ability to level organizational culture in shared goals and vision. This means those teachers have the same level of organizational culture in shared goals and vision.

This affirmed that a strong organizational identity can create a sense of unity that overshadows individual differences. When an organization has a clear set of values and a strong culture, it can align individuals around shared goals and vision, minimizing the impact of demographics. Continuous professional development opportunities provided to all teachers can help standardize their knowledge and skills, leading to a unified approach to education, thereby aligning their perspectives on organizational goals and vision (Weisman et al., 2022).

Table 8

Difference in the Level of Organizational Culture of Private School Teachers in Effective Communication when grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	99	107.37	2933.000	0.000		Significant
	Older	87	77.71				
Civil Status	Single	101	103.10	3322.500	0.008	0.05	Significant
	Married	85	82.09				
Length of Service	Shorter	99	104.86	3182.000	0.002		Significant
	Longer	87	80.57				
Family Income	Lower	91	100.05	3726.000	0.102		Not Significant
	Higher	95	87.22				

Table 8 shows the difference in the level of organizational culture of private school teachers in terms of effective communication.

There was a significant difference that existed when teacher-respondents were grouped according to age, civil status, and length of service, as shown by the computed Mann-Whitney U-Test of 2933.000, 3322.500, 3182.000 and the *p*-value of 0.000, 0.008, and 0.002 which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, being interpreted as "significant." Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of organizational culture of the private school teachers in the area effective communication when grouped according to age, civil status, and length of service was therefore "rejected."

Communication preferences among teachers vary by generation, with older educators favoring traditional methods like face-to-face interaction and younger ones gravitating towards digital platforms.

Marital status also influences communication availability, with single teachers potentially having more time to engage in work-related communications than those with families.

Lastly, teachers with longer tenures bring a depth of knowledge and experience that influences the communication culture, often conveying more authority and impacting organizational dynamics.

These variations in communication styles based on generational differences, civil status, and length of service highlight the complexities of workplace interactions and the need for flexible communication strategies within educational institutions (Millaci, 2017).

Table 9
Difference in the Level of Organizational Culture of Private School Teachers in Rewards and Recognition when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	99	105.53	3115.500	0.001	0.05	Significant
	Older	87	79.81				
Civil Status	Single	101	106.26	3003.500	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Married	85	78.34				
Length of Service	Shorter	99	109.66	2707.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Longer	87	75.11				
Family Income	Lower	91	98.87	3834.000	0.181	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	95	88.36				

Table 9 shows the difference in the level of organizational culture of private school teachers in terms of rewards and recognition.

There was a significant difference that existed when teacher-respondents were grouped according to age, civil status, and length of service, as shown by the computed Mann-Whitney U-Test of 3115.500, 3003.500, 2707.000 and the *p*-value of 0.001, 0.000, and 0.000 which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, being interpreted as "significant." Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of organizational culture of the private school teachers in the area of awards and recognition when grouped according to age, civil status, and length of service was therefore "rejected."

The result indicates that as teachers age, their work values may evolve. Teachers at different stages of their careers value different types of rewards and recognition. Younger teachers prioritize opportunities for professional development, while more experienced teachers might value acknowledgment of their long-term commitment to the school. The significance of rewards and recognition can vary with age because they may be linked to career development opportunities. Younger teachers see rewards as a stepping stone for career advancement, while older teachers might view them as affirmations of their expertise and contributions over the years.

Older and more experienced teachers might have different motivation sources than their younger counterparts. For some, intrinsic rewards such as peer respect and autonomy in the classroom are more valued than extrinsic rewards like bonuses or public accolades. Understanding these motivational factors is crucial for fostering a positive organizational culture that caters to teachers of all ages (Cushman, 2019).

An organizational culture that acknowledges and respects the diversity of civil statuses among its staff promotes a more inclusive environment. Different civil statuses bring different perspectives and experiences, which can enrich the school culture. Civil status can influence the direction and pace of a teacher's professional growth. Single teachers have more flexibility to engage in professional development opportunities that require travel or after-hours commitment, while teachers with families appreciate local or online opportunities.

According to Hameed et al. (2021), organizational behavior and human resources management have repeatedly shown that recognizing and accommodating the diversity of employee circumstances, including civil status, contributes positively to an inclusive workplace culture and can impact professional growth. Studies might explore how flexible work arrangements, which are sensitive to civil status, increase job satisfaction and employee retention. Adaptations demonstrate that the organization values its employees' diverse needs, thereby enhancing commitment and engagement. Similarly, professional development opportunities that accommodate different lifestyles show that an organization recognizes its staff's unique career paths and growth needs.

Teachers with more years of service may have had more professional development and growth opportunities. When an organization recognizes and rewards this growth, it promotes a culture of continuous learning and improvement. Acknowledging the length of service can be seen as an appreciation for a teacher's loyalty and ongoing commitment to the school. It can instill a sense of belonging and encourage retention, reducing turnover rates.

The study titled "Teachers' Affective Well-being and Teaching Experience: The Protective Role of Perceived Emotional Intelligence." suggests that an increased number of years of teaching can be beneficial for some aspects of teacher well-being. Organizational recognition and rewards for long service hints at the positive consequences of greater experience by associating it with teacher effectiveness (Fernández-Berrocal et al., 2017). Also, in "Prioritisation of factors influencing teachers' job satisfaction in the UAE," recognition is highlighted as a top concern for teachers. This implies that when teachers feel recognized—for instance, for their years of service—it could contribute to job satisfaction, which is critical for the retention of teachers (Alkhyeli & Ewijk, 2018).

Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers in Fringe Benefits, Working Environment, and Policies and Guidelines when Grouped according to Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Family Income

Table 10
Difference in the Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers in Fringe Benefits when grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	99	95.34	4124.500	0.618		Not Significant
	Older	87	91.41				
Civil Status	Single	101	105.91	3039.000	0.001	0.05	Significant
	Married	85	78.75				
Length of Service	Shorter	99	95.69	4089.500	0.552		Not Significant
	Longer	87	91.01				
Family Income	Lower	91	94.26	4253.500	0.850		Not Significant
	Higher	95	92.77				

Table 10 portrays the difference in the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers in fringe benefits when grouped according to age, civil status, length of service, and Family Income.

In the area of fringe benefits, when grouped according to the variables of age, length of service, and Family Income, the computed Mann-Whitney U-Test as well as the *p*-values for age (4124.500, 0.618), for the length of service (4089.500, 0.552) and for Family Income (4253.500, 0.850) are higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant."

Therefore, the hypothesis, which states that "there is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers in the area of fringe benefits on the variables of age, length of service and average family monthly, was "accepted."

In the variable of civil status, the computed Mann-Whitney U-Test and the *p*-values are (3039.000, 0.001) lower than the 0.05 significance level, interpreted as "significant."

Therefore, the hypothesis that "there is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers in the area of fringe benefits according to the variable of civil status was "rejected."

This indicates that married teachers, or those with dependents, value fringe benefits differently than single teachers. Benefits like health insurance, retirement plans, and leave policies could be more important to those with families. This is because having dependents typically increases the need for comprehensive benefits to ensure their well-being. Individuals who are married or supporting a family are likely to have a greater economic need for stable and substantial fringe benefits. These benefits are a crucial part of the overall compensation package that can heavily influence job satisfaction.

This was confirmed by the article of Hauck & Wallossek (2020); married individuals or those with dependents are often more risk-averse because they have greater financial obligations. Benefits like health insurance and retirement plans are forms of risk mitigation, offering security for both the employee and their family.

Additionally, employers often tailor their benefits packages to attract and retain the desired employees. It's recognized that offering robust fringe benefits can be particularly attractive to those with families, as it directly contributes to an employee's perceived job security and satisfaction (Fancisco, 2020).

Table 11
Difference in the Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers in Working Environment when grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	99	104.76	3191.500	0.002	0.05	Significant
	Older	87	80.68				
Civil Status	Single	101	95.11	4130.000	0.655	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	85	91.59				
Length of Service	Shorter	99	101.24	3540.500	0.035	0.05	Significant
	Longer	87	84.70				
Family Income	Lower	91	96.58	4042.500	0.442	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	95	90.55				

The table presents the difference in the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers in the working environment when grouped according to age, civil status, length of service, and Family Income.

When grouped according to age and length of service, the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 3191.500 and 3540.500, and the p-values were 0.002 and 0.035, which were lower than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "significant."

This indicates that the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers in the area of working environment according to the variables of age and length of service" was "rejected."

This clearly implies that different age groups have different expectations and values regarding the work environment. Younger teachers seek more innovative, collaborative, and technologically advanced settings, while older teachers appreciate more traditional and stable environments.

With increased length of service, teachers become more accustomed and attached to their school's environment. They develop stronger relationships with colleagues, better understand the school's systems, and feel a greater sense of belonging and comfort, which can boost job satisfaction. Older teachers or those with a longer length of service have witnessed or endured many changes within the school environment.

This conforms with the study of Wanberg (2021) on organizational socialization that employees become more integrated into their social and cultural fabric as they spend more time within an organization, leading to stronger bonds and a heightened sense of belonging.

Additionally, the study of Khaw et al. (2022), entitled "Reactions towards Organizational Change: A Systematic Literature Review," states that organizational change indicates that employees' responses to change can vary widely, with some adapting and others resisting. How these changes are managed and how involved and supported employees feel can significantly impact their job satisfaction.

Table 12
Difference in the Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers in Policies and Guidelines when grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	99	100.96	3568.000	0.042		Significant
	Older	87	85.01				
Civil Status	Single	101	104.65	3166.000	0.002		Significant
	Married	85	80.25				
Length of Service	Shorter	99	99.58	3704.500	0.098	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	87	86.58				
Family Income	Lower	91	101.57	3588.000	0.044		Significant
	Higher	95	85.77				

Table 12 reveals the difference in the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers in policies and guidelines when grouped according to age, civil status, length of service, and Family Income.

The variable of age, civil status, and Family Income got the computed Mann Whitney U test and p-values of (3568.000 and 0.042) for age, (3166.000 and 0.002) for civil status, and (3588.000, 0.044) for Family Income, the p values which was lower than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "significant."

Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers in the area of policies and guidelines according to the variable of age, civil status, and Family Income" was "rejected."

When it comes to age, this implies that younger teachers might be more adaptable to changes in policies and guidelines due to their recent education and familiarity with current educational trends. They are also more open to experimenting with new techniques and approaches that align with evolving policies. Policies and guidelines in today's educational landscape often incorporate technology. Younger teachers, who are typically more tech-savvy, find it easier to comply with technology-driven policies, leading to higher job satisfaction. Age differences can reflect conservative versus progressive attitudes to teaching. Older teachers may prefer established methods and be less satisfied with policies that promote newer approaches, while younger teachers embrace progressive guidelines that reflect modern pedagogy.

Younger teachers are closer to their own educational experiences as students and are, therefore, more likely to have been trained in recent pedagogical trends, making them more open to policies that incorporate such trends into classroom practice (Wesnawa & Christian, 2021).

Regarding civil status, it can affect a teacher's work-life balance. For instance, married teachers have more family obligations that could impact their level of satisfaction concerning the flexibility or inflexibility of school policies and guidelines. Single teachers prioritize career growth and development, and they are more inclined to seek opportunities for advancing in their profession, whereas married teachers prioritize job security and stability.

Married teachers or those with family responsibilities may value workplace policies that offer flexibility, such as parental leave or flexible scheduling, which can significantly impact their job satisfaction. - Single teachers, who may have different personal obligations, could value opportunities for professional development and career advancement, potentially leading them to prioritize jobs that offer growth, which in turn affects their job satisfaction. These studies could explore how family commitments impact the need for certain job resources and how this, in turn, affects job satisfaction (Delavin & Pogoy, 2022).

Lastly, in the Family Income variable, teachers with lower family income face more economic stress, affecting their satisfaction with pay-related school policies. They are more sensitive to the adequacy of compensation, benefits, and financial support provided by the school.

According to Dias et al. (2021), economic theory suggests that individuals who are financially constrained are likely to be more sensitive to wage changes. This may imply that teachers with lower family incomes prioritize the financial aspects of their jobs more than those with higher family incomes. According to Maslow's theory, basic financial security is a fundamental human need. Teachers with lower family incomes might be less likely to feel their needs are met, thus prioritizing salary and benefits in their job satisfaction. Equity Theory proposes that employees who perceive themselves as under-compensated compared to their peers are likely to experience job dissatisfaction. Teachers with lower family incomes might be more acutely aware of disparities in compensation.

Level of Organizational Culture and The Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers

Table 13

Relationship Between the Level of Organizational Culture and the Level of Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers

Variable	Rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of Organizational Culture	1.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
Level of Job Satisfaction				

Table 13 presents the relationship between the level of organizational culture and the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers.

The computed rho-value was 1.000, and the p -value was 0.000, which were lower than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "significant." Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant relationship between the level of organizational culture and the level of job satisfaction of private school teachers" was therefore "rejected."

The result showed that a positive organizational culture can attract high-quality teaching professionals and is crucial for retaining them. Teachers who are satisfied with the school's culture are more likely to remain at the institution, reducing turnover rates. Teachers who are content with the organizational culture tend to be more engaged and motivated, which can contribute to better job performance and, consequently, to higher student achievement.

According to Han et al. (2022), in their "Attraction-Selection-Attrition Framework," this psychological model suggests that organizations attract, select, and retain individuals who fit well with their culture. Applied to schools, this would imply that an organization with a positive culture will attract and retain teachers who share similar values and practices. Within organizational contexts, social exchange theory posits that employees who receive beneficial treatment from their employers feel an obligation to reciprocate with positive behaviors, such as better job performance and greater organizational commitment (Gu & Zhou, 2020).

Conclusion

Generally, a high level of organizational culture and job satisfaction of private school teachers. A significant relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction among private school teachers reflects a solid and supportive work environment where teachers are deeply engaged with the school's mission and values. The findings call to encourage teachers' retention and ensure that teachers stay with the organization, should offer competitive compensation, regularly review, and adjust salaries to ensure they are competitive within the education sector, including possible bonuses or performance incentives.

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